

THE REORGANIZATION OF THE EDUCATION PLANS OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES, IN THE POST-PANDEMIC CONTEXT, BASIS FOR THE EFFICIENT USE OF PUBLIC FUNDS

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Abstract

Purpose – *The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the need for a unified approach at the university level regarding the introduction of courses on medical devices and protective equipment into the educational programs, in order to contribute to the future development of the field.*

Methodology/approach - *The research methods that will be used are the case study.*

Findings – *The importance of this paper can be justified at least by the following arguments: contributes to the development of the stage of knowledge of the theoretical training in the field of medical devices and protective equipment, having direct implications on the performance management of universities, health units and medical staff;*

Research limitations/implications – *Lack of description of the disciplines, within the medical universities.*

Practical implications – *Theoretically, through this paper we want to emphasize that, in the current academic, economic and financial context, in the processes of planning, purchasing and conducting medical acts, decisions on the characteristics of the products used must be made on the basis of theoretical knowledge.*

Originality/value – *We can say that this work is both valuable and original because the claims are not just theoretical. The main author of this paper is not only a theoretician, but a man who worked in the health system during the pandemic and before it, and studied Health Management at UMFST Targu Mures.*

Key words: *medical education, medical devices, PPE*

Introduction

The motivation for choosing this topic was the desire to identify ways to streamline the training process at the level of medical universities, and then in continuing medical training, in the field of medical devices and protective equipment, which faced a number of deficiencies in establishing their minimum characteristics in the pandemic context. These problems were caused by the lack of curricula in medical curricula to study medical devices and equipment, as well as protective equipment. At the same time, within the public procurement procedures, the specialists who draft the specifications that describe the minimum technical characteristics that the products must meet for the proper development of the medical act, are doctors and nurses. Without training in the field of medical devices, protective equipment, in public procurement, they must describe in detail for each product, technical characteristics and minimum standards that the products must meet. It is particularly important for them to know the notions, legislation, and standards of medical devices, not only in terms of efficient use of public funds, by conducting the public procurement process, but also to conduct their medical activity safely for himself, the patient and the medical staff.

The context of the work

"Educational management is the science and art of preparing human resources, to form personalities according to purposes requested by society and accepted by the individual. It presupposes an interdisciplinary approach, which studies the events that intervene in the decision to organize a determined pedagogical activity and in the management of educational programs. Management also involves emphasis on ideas, on a systematic approach, on change, on strategy on innovation." (Nicolae Stan).

With this paper we want to study the existence or non-existence in the curricula of medical universities of courses on the notions, legislation and standards of medical devices and protective equipment. To show the importance of knowing these notions in order to carry out the medical act and the efficiency of the use of public funds.

From an applied perspective, the results obtained from this paper have the role of providing a clear answer to the questions related to the need for a unitary approach at university level on the introduction in the curricula of courses on medical devices and protective equipment.

Also, the topic addressed in this paper is a potential future contribution to the development of the field.

The motivation and importance of this work comes precisely from the perspective of the less happy experiences lived practically in the public health units in Romania, in the context of the two years since the beginning of the COVID 19 crisis, when the medical staff hit the ignorance of these notions of ambiguous, incomplete, overestimated or even contradictory technical characteristics tasks, things that even led to the delay in the completion of tenders.

The subject is motivated, first of all, by the fact that a minimal but thorough training of medical staff in Romania, and in the field of medical devices and protective equipment is absolutely necessary for the medical act, but must be placed in this pandemic context and post-pandemic, and economically present, for the efficient use of public funds, technically and financially, secondly.

Methodology

The research method that will be used is: the case study. R. K. Yin considers that the case study defines "a strategy for conducting research that requires empirical investigations into a particular contemporary phenomenon, in a real life context and using multiple sources of information (interviews, questionnaires, testimonies, evidence, documents)". The main purpose of this study is to show that in the absence of a minimum but thorough training of medical staff in Romania, and in the field of medical devices and protective equipment is absolutely necessary for the performance of the medical act. Therefore, this research paper requires a well-founded theory. In addition, the use of this research method results in evidence and quality facts.

The objectives of the paper

To this end, this paper has the following specific objectives:

1. Conducting an analysis of the existence or non-existence in the study programs of medical universities of courses on the notions, legislation and standards of medical devices and protective equipment.
2. Carrying out an analysis regarding the persons who draw up the description of the specifications in the public health units.

General aspects and theoretical foundations

To keep people healthy and active for longer, for example by providing solutions for disease prevention or early diagnosis, to reduce length of hospital stay, complications, faster recovery, thereby saving time and financial resources of patients, service providers healthcare and the social health insurance system, and to make healthcare systems more efficient, it is necessary to purchase safe, effective and innovative medical devices and technologies by health facilities.

In the procurement and supply processes of medical devices and PPE, the lack of knowledge in this field generates non-compliant practices. They lead to the supply of substandard medical devices and technologies, which cannot be traced. Also, there is the risk of purchasing counterfeit products that do not comply with the legal provisions in force.

There is both European and national legislation transposing European legislation on medical devices and PPE. What is a medical device? In accordance with Regulation (EU) 2017/745 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 April 2017 on medical devices, ("Regulation No. 745/2017") a "medical device" is defined as any instrument, apparatus, machine, computer program, implant, reagent, or other article, intended by the manufacturer to be used, separately or in combination, by human beings for one or more of the following medical purposes: diagnosis, prevention, monitoring, prediction, prognostication, treatment, or amelioration of a disease; diagnosis, monitoring, treatment, amelioration or compensation of an injury or disability; investigation, replacement or modification of an anatomical structure or a physiological or pathological process or condition; providing information through in vitro examination of samples taken from the human body, including organ, blood and tissue donations; and which does not perform its intended primary action by pharmacological, immunological or metabolic means in or on the human body, but which can be assisted in the performance of its function by such means.

The following products are also considered to be medical devices: devices used for the purpose of controlling or promoting conception; products specifically intended for cleaning, disinfecting or sterilizing the devices referred to in Article 1 paragraph (4) of Regulation no. 745/2017, as well as those mentioned in the first paragraph from this point.

Therefore, any material used by doctors, assistants, medical university students, for diagnosis, monitoring, treatment is a medical device. Practical work for this category of person involves the use of medical devices. In order to purchase and supply sanitary units with medical devices and PPE according to the needs of diagnosis, monitoring and treatment, a correct description of them is necessary. This description sets the minimum acceptable standard, to be unambiguous, transparent and not aligned to a particular firm or group of enterprises. The purpose of the specifications is to provide potential suppliers with a clear, accurate and complete description of the needs of health facilities and to meet the needs.

Although the use of the standards is voluntary, with the onset of the pandemic, depending on the level of protection that these products had to meet, they nevertheless became mandatory when they were included as requirements in the award documents. The role of standards in technical specifications was to increase the common understanding of procurement documents between buyers and suppliers.

What is the standard? This is a document, established by consensus and approved by a recognized body, which provides, for common and repeated use, rules, guidelines or characteristics for activities or their results, in order to achieve an optimal degree of order in a given context. Standards can be national, European, international, harmonized. They are identified by the existence of the initials SR, SR EN, SR EN ISO, at the beginning of the standard code.

Therefore, in the Terms of Reference, in relation to the concrete need of the purchase, there must be at least the following: the explanation of any technical or specialized terms, the purpose/how to use the equipment or the product purchased, references to any applicable documents (such as standards or legislation) , material requirements, tolerances or variability, requirements for appearance, texture, finish, conditions of installation, use, production or storage, tolerances for reliability, quality, size, hardness and other key characteristics, measures of quality and performance , test reports, information on labeling in Romanian (name, lot, importer, manufacturer, notified body, lot, validity, sterile, non-sterile, storage conditions) and the application of the CE mark.

Educational management refers to the theory and practice of general management, applied to the education system and process. In this view, education is a kind of company run by one or more managers. However, given the aims of the education system, the complexity of the educational process, the variety and extent of the resources involved and the specificity of the final product which is not a concrete and tangible one, educational management has a particularly pronounced specificity, highlighted, mainly, by what theorists call the human component of process. As a consequence, educational management must be more art than science, because it is not only a service offered to

people (as external subjects of the process), but penetrates into their inner being, causing a change in their psycho-intellectual.

Educational management is "the science and art of preparing human resources, of forming personalities, according to goals accepted by the individual and by society or a certain collective. It includes a set of principles and functions, rules and management methods that ensure the achievement of the objectives of the educational system (as a whole or at the level of the component elements), at the highest standards of quality and efficiency." (John Jinga).

The signatories of the descriptions in the specifications in relation to their training according to the education plans of the medical universities

Who identifies and describes the need for medical devices and protective equipment in public health facilities? After studying the tenders organized by the public health units, from the www.e-licitatie.ro platform, but from the person who works in this field, I concluded that in all cases, they are carried out by specialists. Physicians and assistants users of medical devices and PPE. Going further with the analysis, we studied the complaint files submitted to the National Council for the Resolution of Appeals, by the suppliers, and concluded that the basis of the appeals is the improper description of the products, which do not comply with the minimum requirements presented in the previous chapter. These appeals, as well as the bid evaluation part, greatly delay the procurement process, which can lead to stockouts.

With the onset of the pandemic, the list of protective devices and equipment needed to combat the SARS COV2 virus in health facilities has grown considerably. Products of different protection levels had to be used, according to national, European, international or harmonized standards, which had not been used before. Specialists, doctors and assistants were put in a position to define the need and describe it, for the procurement process. In a regional emergency hospital, doctors and nurses did not have the ability to distinguish medical devices from PPE. They did not know the standards these products had to meet for different levels of protection. They copied the description of some products from other colleagues in the country, requested certain standards, but when evaluating the offers, even those who requested the presence of the standards, did not know what they provided and how they could check if, according to the test reports, these standards were met. There were situations where they chose only the comfort provided by the product, without checking whether the product complies with the level of protection, according to the standards. All these situations led or could lead to the exposure of doctors, nurses and patients to the real danger of infection within health facilities.

Taking into account the previously described, from the desire to identify a possible cause of the lack of knowledge regarding medical devices and PPE, we studied the Education Plans, of the medical universities in Romania (table 1 and 2), to analyze the mandatory subjects, optional and optional from their content. I found that only one university, the "Carol Davila" University of Medicine and Pharmacy from Bucharest, has for its study program general medicine, as an optional discipline for the sixth year, Medical devices.

Therefore, the specialists who should identify needs and describe them, do not have the minimum knowledge of the legislation, regarding medical devices, and on the occasion of the PPE pandemic, which they use in their daily activity, in diagnosis and treatment. This gap existed even before the pandemic period, but it was autized with the onset of the pandemic, creating a real danger.

Conclusions

The importance of this work is justified at least by the following arguments:

- contributes to the development of the stage of knowledge of the theoretical training in the field of medical devices and protective equipment, having direct implications on the performance management of universities, health units and medical staff;
- contributes to the knowledge of the need to study the field of medical devices and protective equipment, of major importance in the management of pandemic situations, and not only;
- highlights the fact that, in the current pandemic, economic and financial context, in the educational, supply and medical process, the correct planning, budgeting and forecasting processes have a special importance, meant to diminish the limits of the decision-making process and performance;

Table 1

Education plan 2021-2027

No	University name	STUDY PROGRAM	The existence of mandatory discipline	The existence of the discipline as optional
1	University of the West Vasile Goldis Arad	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
2	Transylvania University of Braşov	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
3	Ovidius University of Constanta	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
4	University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Grigore T. Popa" Iasi	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
5	UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY,,IULIU HATIEGANU,, CLUJ - NAPOCA	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
6	Oradea University	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
7	"George Emil Palade" University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Sciences and Technology from Târgu Mures	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
8	"CAROL DAVILA" UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY FROM BUCHAREST	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	yes
9	Craiova University of Medicine and Pharmacy	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
10	UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY "VICTOR BABEŞ" TIMISOARA	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no
11	Lucian Blaga University from Sibiu	GENERAL MEDICINE	no	no

Table 2

Education plan 2021-2027

No	University name	STUDY PROGRAM	The existence of mandatory discipline	The existence of the discipline as optional
1	UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY,,IULIU HATIEGANU,, CLUJ - NAPOCA	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
2	University of the West Vasile Goldis Arad	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
3	University of Medicine and Pharmacy "Grigore T. Popa" Iasi	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
4	Oradea University	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
5	Ovidius University of Constanta	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
6	Craiova University of Medicine and Pharmacy	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
7	"George Emil Palade" University of Medicine, Pharmacy, Sciences and Technology from Târgu Mures	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
8	UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE AND PHARMACY "VICTOR BABEŞ" TIMISOARA	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO
9	Lucian Blaga University from Sibiu	GENERAL MEDICAL CARE	NO	NO

- emphasizes that, in the current academic, economic and financial context, in the processes of planning, purchasing and conducting medical acts, decisions on the characteristics of the products used must be made on the basis of theoretical knowledge.

As a result of the difficulties encountered during the pandemic period, the study of the Education Plans, the study of the descriptions in the tenders and the appeals to the tenders, a good practice in the future, as educational, health and financial management, is to analyze the possibility of introducing into the Education Plans, as subjects compulsory study of medical devices and PPE, within the training programs of general medicine and general medical assistance. The real situations experienced in this pandemic should be a lesson in order to solve the identified shortcomings.

An incorrect description of the necessary products, due to a lack of basic training, leads to the purchase of products that do not meet the needs of medical units, which also implies an inefficient use of public funds.

At the same time, the training and updating of knowledge in this field of doctors, nurses and decision-makers in health facilities should not only be carried out at the level of bachelor's and/or master's degrees, but should also be carried out through the College of Doctors and the Order of Medical Assistants.

Through this work, the reality of the curriculum at the level of medical universities was demonstrated in this aspect, the impact on the medical act and it generated recommendations for improving good practices.

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